

To investigate the future of AI in Marketing with reference to Promotion

Ms. Manali Ranade

SBES Research Centre, Chh. Sambhajinagar

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Abstract:

This research investigates the transformative role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in marketing, specifically focusing on its impact on promotional strategies and advertising. As the industry shifts toward data-driven, algorithm-mediated communication, AI is becoming essential for audience targeting, ad creation, and budget optimization. The study explores core technologies, including Machine Learning, Natural Language Processing, and Sentiment Analysis, which provide precise insights into customer behaviour. By analysing case studies from Google, Facebook, and Lexus, the paper demonstrates how AI enhances efficiency and ROI. Ultimately, the research highlights AI's pivotal role in shaping a more competitive, personalized, and efficient future for global advertising.

Introduction:

Change is the one constant in life. And at this very moment, the marketing industry is undergoing a massive transformation. With the introduction of generative AI platforms like ChatGPT and intelligent marketing tools, artificial intelligence (AI) marketing is becoming more prevalent. This presents marketing teams with a plethora of chances to expand on their existing areas of expertise. For marketers, this is a crucial benefit.

AI marketing offers incredibly accurate insights into your customer journey and market trends by fusing AI technologies with customer and brand experience data. Artificial intelligence (AI) technologies, such as sentiment analysis, machine learning (ML), natural language processing (NLP), and others, help you make decisions that keep you ahead of the competition and ready for the demands of a changing market.

Advertising is evolving due to artificial intelligence (AI). AI is changing every aspect of the advertising business, including audience targeting, ad buying, and ad development and testing. Advertising context is greatly impacted, and AI-driven advertising has emerged as a viable new medium in high-profile sectors like retail, automotive, entertainment, healthcare, pharmaceuticals,

telecommunications, and financial services. The idea of advertising powered by AI is becoming more and more common.

Objectives:

1. to grasp the application of AI in advertisements.
2. to know the different techniques used by AI in advertisements.

Research Question:

- Does AI have a place in the world of advertising?

Data Interpretation:

Advertising research develops the understanding of the efficiency, effectiveness, and safety of how and why AI operates in advertising. Intelligent advertising is defined as consumer-centered, data-driven, and algorithm-mediated brand communication. AI is predicted to take up to 80 percent of Global advertising spend in the world. Around 75% advertisers use AI in their services. In 2018, Lexus released the first advertisement scripted by artificial intelligence. Lexus used IBM Watson to analyse 15 years of “car and luxury brand campaigns that have won Cannes Lions awards for creativity.

Facebook advertising provides ad frequency and relevance score. These two numbers are key pieces of data that Facebook's algorithms use as no human involvement is there to dictate how much we pay and how our ads are displayed. Machine learning algorithms are used by commercially available solutions to analyse how various ads perform across specific platforms, then offer recommendations on how to improve performance. The AI tool, Albert uses sophisticated AI to analyse ad campaigns, then manage targeting, testing, and budgets. Another AI tool, Phrasee is used for ad creation.

Google has introduced advertising campaign processes and the automatic creation of ads through the utilization of Learning Language Models (LLM) and generative AI within Google Ads.

According to Dan Taylor, the Vice President of Global Ads at Google, leading companies such as Mynta, Samsung, HDFC, and Tata AIG have witnessed growth rates of up to 18 per cent through the use of Performance Max. This advertising tool incorporates Google's AI technologies for bidding, budget optimization, audience targeting, creative development, and attribution.

Archana Jain, the Founder and Managing Director of PR Pundit, an integrated communications consultancy firm, emphasized that public relations must embrace the ongoing transformation fuelled by AI. She believes that the PR industry is on the brink of experiencing further disruptions in the upcoming years.

Jain highlighted the benefits of AI in PR, stating that professionals can now analyze vast amounts of data rapidly and efficiently. This ability enables them to make well-informed decisions and develop more effective PR strategies. Additionally, AI facilitates the creation of innovative content tailored to digitally-focused target audiences. Even in fundamental tasks like media coverage tracking, AI plays a pivotal role in enhancing overall efficiency within the industry.

Powerful social marketing platforms, like Sprout, weave together sophisticated AI technologies under the hood to provide the insights you need to succeed. Capabilities such as semantic classification, named entity recognition and aspect-based sentiment analysis help you get targeted insights specific to your industry, while natural language processing helps you optimize social content and improve customer engagement—all leading to greater competitive advantage and share of voice.

Following are some technologies to explain above mentioned points better.

1. Machine learning:

Machine learning (ML) uses statistical methods to analyze social data for high-precision insights around customer experience, audience sentiment and other marketing drivers. Once trained, ML models automatically complete text mining, topic extraction, aspect classification, semantic clustering and other tasks to provide results in seconds.

AI-ML models get smarter as they process more data over time and so upgrade automatically, which is perfect for scaling your business operations while minimizing future investment in your tech stack.

2. Natural language processing (NLP):

Natural language processing powers your AI marketing tool so it can semantically and contextually understand social listening data. It combines rules-based lexical and statistical methods, enabling you to scan a wide range of posts, messages, reviews or comments and extract critical information from it.

When NLP algorithms are coded for social listening, they can interpret the data even if it's splattered with colloquialisms, code switches, emojis, abbreviations, hashtags or spelling mistakes. Natural language generation (NLG) further enhances the tool's capabilities to help you create high-performing copy for posts, customer responses and more.

This gives you access to a wider audience for outreach campaigns, stronger communication with existing customers and better returns on our investment in social.

3. Semantic search:

Semantic search algorithms are critical in NLP because they help understand the intent of a phrase or lexical string without depending on keywords. These algorithms extract relevant keywords and categorize them into semantic clusters. This eliminates chances of duplicates in text mining, especially where sentiment analysis is concerned, for an accurate measure of customer experience or brand performance.

Knowing exactly how strong your brand is in relation to your competitors and monitoring it against your benchmarks can help you alter marketing and sales strategies to achieve long-term business goals.

4. Named entity recognition (NER) and neural networks:

NER helps an AI platform identify named entities in big data. These entities could be important people, places or things such as CEOs, celebrities, locations, currencies, businesses and others. It can identify these entities even if they are misspelled. NER also is a key function in generating knowledge graphs because they establish a relationship between entities in order to derive context and insights from data.

Neural network (NN) algorithms, built to mimic how a human brain handles information, remember these interconnected data points and keep adding them to their knowledge database. This is what enables ML models to provide more precise results with time through deep learning.

Thus, you get to know why certain brands keep appearing in your social listening data, what new market trends are brewing, which influencers would be a great fit and many other insights that can help you strengthen your social marketing strategy.

5. Sentiment analysis:

Sentiment analysis is the process of measuring customer sentiment from feedback data and can be instrumental in helping with reputation management. Sentiment analysis algorithms analyze social listening data including survey responses, online reviews and incoming messages, both in real-time and historically. They measure sentiment in every aspect that is extracted from the data and assign polarity scores in the range of -1 to +1. Neutral statements are counted as zero.

When analyzing social data where customers are talking about aspects of a business, sentiment analysis models consider the polarity score of each aspect. These **sentiment scores are aggregated** to provide an overall sentiment of the brand in terms of customer experience. This eventually gives you an idea of how well your business is performing.

With such insights available, you can grow your brand by evaluating and improvising social media content, shaping sales and marketing, improving brand management, better interpreting customer intent and so much more.

What is the future of AI in marketing?

AI marketing is achieving new advancements at a phenomenal speed. Here are some ways it's reshaping businesses for the better.

Computer vision:

Computer vision allows AI marketing tools to derive insights from non-text digital data available in the form of raw images. From powering optical character recognition (OCR) to analyze information and signatures in checks and recognize brand logos in videos, to extracting text from images for accessibility, computer vision is helping solve key business challenges every day.

AI chatbots:

Conversational AI in the form of virtual agents and intelligent chatbots is set to change traditional marketing. **AI chatbot marketing** can put brand visibility in hyperdrive with targeted messaging. They can boost engagement with

existing customers and prospects to generate leads and also analyze their data to provide you with fine-grained insights for predictive and prescriptive marketing.

Virtual agents also streamline customer requests, ensure 24/7 customer support and route conversations to the appropriate team for the best results—all resulting in increased customer satisfaction and loyalty.

Predictive and prescriptive AI:

Predictive and prescriptive analytics are already making AI marketing tools essential for marketers. Prescription analytics sorts social listening data into categories based on consumer motivations, mindsets and intentions. This information from **conversational analytics** enables businessman to develop highly targeted ads, posts and emails that will yield optimal results. A great example of this is how streaming services use your previous choices to provide you with content relevant to your interests.

Predictive analytics enables businessman to go further sohe/she can anticipate outcomes and develop a business strategy well in advance based on past voice of customer data. This means you can build long-term business models, conduct risk evaluations, expand market acquisitions, improve product designs and more.

Responsible AI:

AI marketing also takes into account the fact that existing AI models are not perfect. To achieve true advantages and accuracy in deriving business insights, AI in business needs to be fair, secure, reliable, inclusive and transparent. This means that AI tools need to be developed more thoughtfully and trained with diverse data to remove biases.

Build impactful business strategies with AI:

AI marketing insights are empowering businesses to build a foundation for growth and future success by exploring new marketing, product and customer engagement opportunities. AI technologies like sentiment analysis, NLP, virtual agents and others are determining how efficiently

you reach business goals, from revenue optimization to navigating unpredictable market scenarios.

With targeted AI-driven customer insights you can develop a more proactive social media marketing approach to drive customer engagement, loyalty and retention. And ultimately market growth.

Audience segmentation and personalization:

AI marketing can drive business strategies based on market segmentation, aligning campaigns with customers who are most likely to buy your product or offering. Businessman can also leverage programmatic advertising to streamline the process of selecting and setting up digital ads for the most return on investment (ROI). This enables more personalized marketing tactics to nurture brand loyalty and create powerful brand awareness campaigns.

Data analysis for customer insights:

AI and machine learning give critical customer insights on a range of aspects to help businessman to make strategic marketing decisions. Get deep insights into audience sentiment around your brand, and a full audit of your customer care team's performance and **social media engagement metrics**.

This can empower businessman to quickly adapt to changing market trends, prioritize budgets based on what aspects need the most investment and deepen customer relationships.

Reputation management:

When it comes to brand reputation, let's be honest, there are some things in the control of businessman. Social media has made brands more susceptible to scrutiny than ever before. But with AI-enabled **brand reputation management**, Businessman can avert a potential brand threat before it turns into a big issue.

Competitive intelligence:

AI tools can help businessman to spot opportunities to improve their products and offerings, and fill market gaps. Discern their competitors' share of voice and find smart ways to

be agile in a competitive market. Also, compare business' social performance to the competitors via **competitive benchmarking**.

Multilingual advantage:

A global presence must take into account cross-cultural elements along with providing prompt and efficient customer care. **AI marketing tools** can extract customer insights from multilingual data effortlessly so you know which strategy will likely be the most successful in a particular geography. You can also ensure your intended audience finds your social posts, responses and advertisements relatable and adhering to their cultural standards.

Conclusion:

From the above information we can say that many firms now use AI to handle narrow tasks, such as digital ad placement, assist with broad tasks, like enhancing the accuracy of predictions and augment human efforts in structured tasks, such as customer service.

With targeted AI-driven customer insights businessman can develop a more proactive social media marketing approach to drive customer

engagement, loyalty and retention. And ultimately market growth. As well as he/she can build long-term business models, conduct risk evaluations, expand market acquisitions, improve product designs and more.

So we can say that AI has a lot of potential applications in the marketing sector, namely in advertising.

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